

Spectrophotometric determination of copper(II) and nickel(II) using thiosemicarbazone of citral

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Manuscript received 17 March 2006, revised 6 April 2006, accepted 10 April 2006

Abstract : Thiosemicarbazone of citral, a condensation product of industrially and ecofriendly terpenoid serve as very good analytical reagent for biologically important metal copper and nickel. The analytical properties of thiosemicarbazone of citral (CDOTSC) are described for the first time. The reagent gives brown colour complex with copper and grey colour complex with nickel in sodium acetate buffer medium of 5.6 and 2.6 respectively. The molar absorptivities of copper and nickel complexes respectively are 8.75×10^3 and $1.25 \times 10^4 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. These colour reactions have been investigated for the spectrophotometric determination of copper(II) and nickel(II) in aqueous medium.

Keywords : Spectrophotometry, copper(II), nickel(II), thiosemicarbazone.

In continuation of our previous work on terpenoids and their derivatives¹ here in we report the spectrophotometric determination of the thiosemicarbazone of citral (3,7-dimethyl-2,6-octadien-1-al) with copper(II) and nickel(II). The reagent is applied for the determination of copper in synthetic alloys.

Thiosemicarbazone of 3,7-dimethyl-2,6-octadien-1-al (CDOTSC)

Results and discussion

The citral chemically known as 3,7-dimethyl-2,6-octadien-1-al, thiosemicarbazone derivative of this citral (CDOTSC) is easily prepared under reflux conditions². In basic medium the ligand presumably exists in enolic form and co-ordinates the divalent metal ion as mono anion. The reagent gives intense colour reaction only with copper and nickel and show maximum absorbance at 373 and 376 nm respectively. The reagent is considered as potential reagent for selective spectrophotometric determination of copper(II) and nickel(II).

Determination of copper and nickel : Copper(II) and nickel(II) reacts with CDOTSC in acidic pHs to give brown and grey coloured complexes. The order of addition of reagent, metal ion, buffer has no effect on the absorbance of the complexes provided DMF is added prior to the addition of reagent solution. The absorbances of the coloured complexes remain constant for 6 h. A 5-fold molar excess of the reagent is adequate for full colour development. Addition of excess reagent has no adverse affect of the absorbance of the complexes.

The system obeys Beer's law in the concentration range 0.53–4.3, 0.46 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of copper and nickel respectively. The optimum range for the determination of copper(II) and nickel(II) from Ringbom's plot is found to be 0.27–0.87, 0.32–0.72 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity of the method for Cu and Ni found to be 8.85×10^3 , $1.29 \times 10^4 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and 0.073, 0.085 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ respectively. The specific absorptivity of the system is 0.133, 0.127 $\text{ml}^{-1} \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for Cu and Ni respectively. The relative standard deviation for ten replicate analyses Cu and Ni are 0.25 and 0.28% respectively. Job's and molar ratio methods gave the composition of the Cu and Ni complexes as 1 : 2, 1 : 1 (M : L) respectively. The stability constants of Cu and Ni complexes calculated by Job's method are found to be 8.1×10^5 and 5.8×10^4 respectively.

Interferences : The effects of some of the ions which often accompany copper and nickel has been studied by

adding different amounts of anions and cations to 0.74 and 2.46 (ppm) $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of copper and nickel in solution. The colour is developed as described in the recommended procedure an error of $\pm 2\%$ in the absorbance reading is considered tolerable. (Larger amounts of iron(III) does not interfere in the presence of fluoride, masking reagent). The tolerance limit of foreign ions in the determination of 0.74 and 2.46 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of copper and nickel are (fluoride 72–36, chloride 137–137, tartrate 897–596, bromide 315–315, carbonate 235–235, cyanate 107–107, iodate 505–504, acetate 183–183, thiourea 0.7–6, Mo^{VI} 92–61, sulphate 981–381, nitrate 240–122, thiocyanate 0.3–26, Ce^{IV} 3–5, Fe^{II} 34–25, oxalate 0.3–23, Hg^{II} 0.5–1, Ag^{I} 8–4, Th^{IV} 42–43, Mn 22–24, Ni^{II} 23–..., Co^{II} 12–16, V^{V} 2–2, Pd^{II} 58–58, Sn^{II} 4–0.3, Cd^{II} 8–16, Cr^{IV} 2–0.7, Zn 24–24, Cu^{II} ...–0.8, Al^{III} 12–0.02, Zr^{IV} 21–27, W^{VI} 72–72, Ca^{II} 14–14, Ba^{II} 51–72) respectively.

Determination of copper in NTPC alloy sample : The amount of copper present in synthetic samples whose composition corresponding to NTPC and aluminium alloys was determined by using the present method. The results are : NTPC alloy^a : taken (0.448, 0.911, 1.831), found^b (0.428, 0.867, 1.719) mg/ml. Al alloy^c : taken (1.008, 2.011, 3.21), found (0.996, 1.999, 3.106) ("Composition of NTPC alloy Ni, 10; Cr, 15; Fe, 6.5; Cu, 4.5; Mn 2%. ^bAverage of 3 determinants. ^cComposition of aluminium alloy Ni, 1.88; Cu, 4.12; Fe, 0.6; Mn, 0.2; Mg, 1.6 and rest Al).

Conclusion :

The reagent provides a simple rapid and accurate method for the spectrophotometric determination of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} . The reagent has the advantage of high sensitivity, selectivity and easy availability.

Experimental

Thiosemicarbazone of citral (3,7-dimethyl-2,6-oxadiene-1-al) was prepared by dissolving the thiosemicarbazide (10 mmol) in 5% aqueous AcOH (30 cm^3) on a boiling water bath. The solution was slowly added with stirring to a freshly prepared solution of 3,7-dimethyl-2,6-octadien-1-al (10 mmol) in EtOH (20 cm^3 , 95%). After refluxing for 1 h the reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature and a yellow precipitated obtained. It was characterised by elemental analysis, IR and EPR spectral data.

The reagent solution (0.01 M) was prepared by dissolving 100 mg of the compound in 50 ml of dimethylformamide and it is stable for 36 h. Hydrochloric acid (1 ml), sodium acetate (1 ml) pH (0.7–3.7), 0.2 M NaOAc, 0.2 M AcOH (pH 4–6) and 2 M NH_4Cl , 2 M NH_4OH buffer solutions were used in the present study. The standard copper(II) and nickel(II) solutions (1×10^{-2} M) were prepared by using analytical reagent grade $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ respectively. The stock solutions of copper(II) and nickel(II) were standardised using titrimetric and gravimetric methods³ respectively.

Schimidzu 160 A UV-visible spectrophotometric equipped with 1.0 cm quartz cells Elico-model LI 120 pH meter were used in present study.

The reactions of some important metal ions were tested at different pH values. The samples were prepared in 25 ml volumetric flask by mixing 10 ml of buffer, 1 ml of metal ion and 1 ml of 0.01 M CDOTSC solution. The reaction mixture was diluted to mark with distilled water. The absorbance was measured in 250–600 nm range against the reagent blank.

An aliquot metal ion in the Beer's law validity range (0.53–4.3 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ Cu, 0.46–4.5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ Ni), 10 ml of buffer solution (pH 5.6 for Cu and pH 2.6 for Ni) and 1 ml of 1×10^{-2} M CDOTSC solution were taken in 25 ml standard flask and diluted to the mark with distilled water. The absorbance to the coloured solution was measured at corresponding wave length (373 and 376 nm for Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} respectively) against reagent blank. Calibration graphs were prepared. The measured absorbance values were used to compute the amount of copper and nickel present in the unknown solution.

References

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